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Analyzing Potential of Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) Strains under Drought Milieu for Seedlings Traits

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Abstract

Wheat is globally known king among small grain cereals due to its high consumption and demand. Wheat has higher nutritive value for daily diet. The demand of this ancient cereal is rising with day to date increase in population. Wheat crop is facing yield constraints that limit production due to climatic change. The climate change involved in fluctuations linked with availability of water supply. This climate challenge tends to increase the drought stress for crop production. The current research was planned to screen the stock of wheat accessions under drought milieu to cope against the climate peril to wheat production. Hundred and two genotypes were evaluated on seedling traits e.g. RL (root length), SL (shoot length), FW (fresh shoot weight), DW (dry shoot weight), R/S % (root to shoot ratio) and RWC (relative water content). The accessions were evaluated under control and drought. The findings showed significant result of accessions performance for seedling traits under drought stress. Under drought stress root length varied from (5.03 cm to 17.50 cm), shoot length varied from (11.20 cm to 25 cm), fresh shoot weight varied from (0.28 g to 0.86 g), dry shoot weight varied from (0.10 g to 0.30 g), root to shoot % varied from (0.27 % to 0.91 %) and relative water contents varied from (53.66 % to 73 %). Direct selection can be recommended on the base of seedling traits for drought tolerance to figure out valued strains of wheat.

Keywords: Clime change, drought stress, wheat accessions, valued strains

INTRODUCTION

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is very important grain cereal for human & animal nutrition and being a major cereal crop for production wise since prehistoric time, wheat also ranks second among cereal after the rice in the world cereal crop production (Maier et al., 2017; Zampieri et al., 2017). Wheat is a staple food for 1/3rd world's population (Abd-El-Haleem et al., 2009). Wheat comprised of essential dietary nutrients e.g. 70% carbohydrates, 22% fibers, 12% water, 12% proteins, 2% fat and 1.8% minerals (Mahpara, 2008). Speeding population growth results increase in the demand of wheat production, which is expected will increase 50% demand of wheat production by 2030 to fulfill the dietary needs population (Gahlaut et al., 2017). Drought is one of the limiting constrains for the wheat production and caused a obvious decline in the wheat productivity (Farooq et al., 2014). The drought stress caused severe yield losses and badly affect the normal crop stand (Hussain et al., 2018). The 92% yield losses due to drought in wheat was reported (Farooq et al., 2014).

Water is an essential need of every metabolic activity for natural plant growth. Water scarcity raises serious concerns for sustainable agriculture worldwide under arid and semi-arid areas (Sharafi et al., 2011). The selection and screening of tolerant lines for water stress environment helps to sustain better growth under drought stress (Zaharieva et al., 2001). Severe affects on the crop stand at seedling stage of wheat was reported due to drought stress (Nezhadahmadi et al., 2013). This study was conducted to screen genotypes for drought tolerance from the available stocks to initiate a breeding scheme for development of novel crosses.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Hundred and two genotypes of bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) containing cultivars and advance lines from diverse background were selected from the available stock of UAF (University of Agri. Faisalabad). All the genotypes were planted in two water regimes, under normal and water stress. The genotypes were planted in the polythene bags in triplicate manner. The normal genotypes were attaining water 620 ml which is 100% field capacity of the polythene bag of size 30×15. Whereas genotypes in water stress regime were watered 310 ml which is the 50% field capacity of the bags used for plantation. The genotypes were under both environments were grown for four weeks to data of seedling traits were taken. The studied traits include e.g. SL (shoot length), RL (root length), R/S % (root to shoot %), FW (fresh weight), DW (dry weight) and RWC (relative water content). The data was analyzed by using statistics software for significance (Steel et al., 1997).

RESULTS

Significant differences were reported in the genotypes for seedling attributes (Table 1). The treatment affect were observed highly significant. However, interaction of genotypes with environment showed significant relationship.

Table 1. Mean square values for ANOVA (analysis of variance)

S.O.V	D.F	RL	SL	R/S %	FW	DW	RWC
Replication	2	0.18	0.13	0.036	0.766	0.001	9.3
Genotypes	101	57.39**	40.63**	0.17*	0.04**	0.02**	101.9*
Treatment	1	1782.31**	3246.23*	0.2*	27.78**	1.93**	15841.7**
G×T	101	5.81*	6.11*	0.052*	0.23**	0.018*	2.2**
Error	406	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.005	0.001	0.7

The study showed that water stress has a negative effect on the seedling traits of wheat accessions. The mean performance of genotypes was greatly declined due to water stress (Table 2). The trait root length showed a mean value of 11.87cm under normal which is higher than the mean 8.45cm under water stressed regime. Genotypes identified for longer RL (root length) under normal and water stress were Bakhar-2002, Chakwal-50, Chakwal-86, Lasani-2008, Faisalabad-2008, 9797, Miraj-2008, Sehar-2006, 9488 and 9633. Water stress showed a decline of 28.81% in mean performance of genotypes for root length under water deficit regime (Fig 1). Shoot length mean in normal was higher 22.48cm than the mean 17.87cm under water stressed. The 20.50% reduction in the mean of shoot length under water deficit was observed as compared mean performance under normal environment (Fig 2). Genotypes identified for longer SL (shoot length) were BARS-2009, Chakwal-86, Lasani-2008, Faisalabad-2008 and Sehar-2006. Root to shoot % showed a decrease of mean value from normal 0.53 to 0.47 under water deficit condition. Genotypes showed high root to shoot % under water deficit condition were Aas-2002, 9805, 9479, Chakwal-86, 9797 and 9493. The water stress caused 11.32% decline in the mean performance of genotypes for root to shoot % (Fig 3). The drought caused a decrease in the fresh weight of shoot from 0.97g under normal environment to 0.54g under water deficit condition. Following genotypes e.g. Miraj-2008, 9859, 9501, 9797 and 9493 were identified for high fresh weight under drought stress. Drought declined the mean performance 55.67% of accessions for fresh weight under water stress (Fig 4). Dry weight mean 0.27g of accessions in normal environment was observed higher than 0.15g in water deficit condition. Genotypes i.e. 9493, 9479, 9859 and Shahkar-95 were identified as higher performer for dry weight in water stress. Water deficit environment caused 55.55% decrease in the mean performance of accessions for dry weight (Fig 5). RWC (relative water content) mean for normal regime was noticed higher 72.60% as compared to water deficit mean 61.24%. The genotypes showed higher performance for relative water contents were identified e.g. Chakwal-50, Bakhar-2002, Chakwal-86, Lasani-2008, Faisalabad-2008, 9797, Miraj-2008, Sehar-2006, 9618, 9488 and 9633., RWC (relative water contents) showed decline of 15.64% in mean performance of genotypes under water stress (Fig 6).

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Table 2. Normal and stress regime performance statistics

Traits	Conditions	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
RL	Normal	6.06	23.20	11.87
	Drought	5.03	17.50	8.45
SL	Normal	13.10	29.24	22.48
	Drought	11.20	25.00	17.87
R/S %	Normal	0.28	0.94	0.53
	Drought	0.27	0.91	0.47
FW	Normal	0.76	1.20	0.97
	Drought	0.28	0.86	0.54
DW	Normal	0.14	0.58	0.27
	Drought	0.10	0.30	0.15
RWC	Normal	63.33	85.30	72.60
	Drought	53.66	73.00	61.24

Figure 1. Mean comparison of root length under normal and drought regime

Figure 2. Mean comparison of shoot length under normal and drought regime

Figure 3. Mean comparison of root to shoot ratio under normal and drought regime

Figure 4. Mean comparison of fresh weight under normal and drought regime

Figure 5. Mean comparison of dry weight under normal and drought regime

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Figure 6. Mean comparison of relative water content under normal and drought regime

CORRELATION

Correlation among seedling traits was studied under normal and drought to develop indirect selection strategy (Table 3 & 4). Under control regime, simple correlation coefficients for root length showed highly positively and significant association with root to shoot %, fresh weight and dry weight. While root length showed negative association with relative water content and shoot length. Shoot length showed significant positive association with relative water content, while shoot length showed negative correlation with all except relative water contents. Root to shoot % showed positive association with all except shoot length and relative water content which are negatively correlated. Fresh weight showed negative correlation with relative water content and shoot length. Whereas fresh weight showed positive and significant association with root length, root to shoot% and dry weight. Dry weight showed positive association with root length, root to shoot% and fresh weight. Dry weight showed negative correlation with shoot length and relative water. Trait relative water content showed negative association with all except shoot length. Under drought stress (Table 4), root length showed positive association with all except root to shoot% which showed negative correlation with root length. Shoot length showed non significant association all traits. Root to shoot% showed positive but non significant correlation with fresh weight and dry weight. While root to shoot% showed negative association with root length, shoot length and relative water content. Fresh weight showed positive association with root length, dry weight and relative water content. Dry weight showed positive correlation with fresh weight and root length. Relative water content showed positive and highly significant association with fresh weight, dry weight and root length.

Table 3. Correlation among seedling traits under control environment

Variables	RL	SL	R/S %	FW	DW
SL	-0.125 ^{ns}				
R/S %	0.899**	-0.217*			
FW	0.452**	-0.190 ^{ns}	0.398**		
DW	0.587**	-0.042 ^{ns}	0.617**	0.605**	
RWC	-0.312**	0.415**	-0.296*	-0.702**	-0.221**

Table 4. Correlation among seedling traits under drought stress

Variables	RL	SL	R/S %	FW	DW
SL	0.041 ^{ns}				
R/S %	-0.017 ^{ns}	-0.173 ^{ns}			
FW	0.188*	-0.152 ^{ns}	0.166 ^{ns}		
DW	0.329**	-0.163 ^{ns}	0.042 ^{ns}	0.773**	
RWC	0.314**	-0.177 ^{ns}	-0.018 ^{ns}	0.921**	0.876**

** = Highly significant, * = Significant, ^{ns} = non significant

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RL= root length, SL= shoot length, R/S %= root to shoot ratio, FW= fresh weight, DW= dry weight, RWC= relative water content

DISCUSSION

Adverse effect on plant growth and development was reported due to drought stress (Wahid et al., 2007). Plants showed changes in its pathways to adjust itself in water stress (Chaves et al., 2009). Change in environment caused changes in the genotypic behavior of plant physiology and morphology (Nasees et al., 2015; Sharif et al., 2019). Plants need optimum supply of moisture to maintain relative moisture content, lack of optimum supply decreases moisture contents. The decrease in moisture contents in plants caused lose of turgor pressure (Lonbani and Arzani, 2011). The trigger in root length enhancement is a response of physiological adjustment in the plants under drought milieu (Siddig et al., 2013). Shoot length is a crucial attribute for drought studies. Shoot and shoot length has a positive role in the plant growth and survival (Taiz and Zeiger, 2014). The adverse effect on the shoot length and significant decrease was noted in shoot length under water deficit (Ahmad et al., 2013). The selection under drought can be done on the base of root to shoot length. The selection of tolerant and high performing genotypes for root to shoot % can be good selection strategy on seedling. The good performer showed less decrease in root to shoot % under water stress (Rauf et al., 2006). The fresh weight is the reliable parameter to estimate plant performance under water stress. Decline in fresh weight of shoot was observed in water deficit milieu (Khakwani et al., 2011). Water deficit regime cause a significant reduction in plant biomass (Mujtabad et al., 2016). High contents of relative water is a pretty good indicator of tolerance under drought (Schonfeld et al., 1988). Reduction in plants relative water contents under drought regime was reported (Cornic, 2000). Selection of wheat accessions based on the said traits were found useful for drought tolerance.

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